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INTERNATIONAL EDUCATION RESEARCH

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INNOVATIVE ECOLOGICAL EDUCATION OF ECO-AESTHETIC CULTURE AMONG FUTURE EDUCATORS

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Annotation. The article discusses the innovative ecological education of eco- aesthetic culture among future educators.

Key words: Formation, values, form, development, ethics, personality, reschooler, eco-aesthetics, development factors

INTRODUCTION

Today, one of the strategically important issues of education is the environmental education of the younger generation. The content of the educational field "Cognition" is aimed at forming primary ideas about the objects of the surrounding world, their properties and relationships (shape, color, size, causes and effects, etc.); about the planet Earth as a common home of people, about the peculiarities of its nature, the diversity of countries and peoples; expanding the horizons of children. The content of the educational field "Speech development" involves familiarity with children's literature, including natural history.

The educational field "Artistic and aesthetic development" involves the formation of prerequisites for value-semantic perception and understanding of the natural world; the formation of an aesthetic attitude to the surrounding world as a whole. The educational field "Physical development" is aimed at establishing the values of a healthy lifestyle among preschoolers. Interaction of preschoolers with nature in the process of environmental education develops the child's psyche, motor activity and makes him physically stronger and healthier. Along with traditional forms and methods of environmental education in our pedagogical activities (conversations, observations, reading literature, reviewing, direct educational activities, practical activities) we also use innovative forms and methods. Here are examples of various innovative di-

rections of ecological education of preschoolers.

LITERATURE AND METHODS

1. "Environmental games"

The ecological game helps the teacher to convey the meaning of complex natural phenomena to children in a more accessible form; develops cognitive abilities in children; clarifies, consolidates, expands children's ideas about objects and phenomena of nature, plants, animals. Games can be played with children both collectively and individually, complicating them taking into account the age of children. Didactic games are held during leisure hours, during classes and walks.

I attach an ecological character to the content of story-role-playing games: "To the forest for mushrooms and berries", "Fishing with my grandfather", "A trip through the mountains", "To my grandmother's garden", etc.

Puzzle games, experiment games, research games, meditation games ("I am a daisy flower", "I am autumn rain", "I am a little frog", "I am a farmer" and others) give new impressions about the life and work of people, about the state of nature and its changes; arouse interest in nature and develop a value attitude towards it; form motives and practical skills of environmentally appropriate activities. They provide children with opportunities for independence, initiative, cooperation, responsibility and the ability to make the right decisions. In these games, children apply their life expe-

rience and reflect what interests, excites, and pleases them.

2. "Letter of complaint"

An interesting technique in working with children is to receive letters of complaint from residents of a living corner, residents of a forest, garden, vegetable garden - those who need human help and protection. When receiving such a letter, children think about its content, discuss various environmental situations, decide how to help a particular living being, forest, river, etc. How to protect and protect nature – your region and the whole planet.

3. "Case technology".

The "Case technology" method is an analysis of a situation or a specific case, a business game. Its main purpose is to develop the ability to analyze various problems and find solutions to them, as well as the ability to work with information.

Case technologies develop communicative competencies in those educational areas where there is no unambiguous answer to the question posed, but there are several answers, and you need to find the right answer by arguing your arguments.. For example, a case photo or a case illustration "Does a child behave correctly in nature?"

The game "Find out by ads" introduces the features of animals and birds (appearance, behavior, habitat), develops logical thinking. Children listen attentively to the announcement, and guess who it is about (animal or bird).

Examples of ads:

- I am a swamp berry, orange in color. I consist of a lot of juicy balls.
- A coniferous tree has been lost, which throws off needles for the winter.
- Come to visit me! I don't have an address. I always carry my house on myself.
- Friends! Who needs needles, contact me.

The business game "Good – bad" improves children's knowledge about the phenomena of living and inanimate nature, animals and plants: "Is a mosquito good or bad?", "Is a swamp good or bad",

"Trees without leaves in winter – is it good or bad?" and so on.

The business game "Hunters" shows children that everything is connected in nature. I suggest one child to arrange animals that hunt each other in a certain sequence. Other children also help to find the right pictures with animals. You can suggest starting the game with a plant, a frog or a mosquito.

The business game "What will happen if ...?" helps to find out what needs to be done in order to protect, preserve and multiply nature, develops the ability to draw conclusions and conclusions. For example: what happens if a boy throws a can of lemonade into the river? And two? And three? Are there many boys? What will happen if one family brings an armful of primroses from the forest on a weekend? Two families? Five? What happens if one driver's car emits a lot of exhaust gases? Three cars? Half of the city's drivers? What happens if you don't put out the fire in the forest?

Business game "Take care of nature". On a table or a blackboard I place pictures depicting plants, birds, animals, man, sun, water, etc. I remove one of the pictures, and the children have to tell me what will happen to the remaining living objects if there is no hidden object on Earth. For example: we remove the bird – what will happen to the rest of the animals, with man, with plants, etc.

4. "IOS"

I also use game training situations (IOS) with fairy-tale characters in my work: "Firebird talks to children about trees", "Winnie-the-Pooh goes to the meadow for honey", "A Distracted person gets acquainted with indoor plants", "Cipollino conducts experiments with onions". Game-based learning situations such as travel also arouse cognitive interest in nature. Travel is the collective name of various kinds of games in visiting, trips, hiking. Visiting interesting places - forests, zoos, museums, farms, children get new knowledge about nature in a playful way.

6. "Method of ecological identification"

"Method of ecological identification" - identification with any natural object or phenomenon, a game technique of "transformation" into images of animals, plants, actions on their behalf. Having been in the role of any object or object of nature, the child begins to treat him with respect. For example, playing the situation "I am an ant... ", "I am a broken tree... ", "I am a chick that fell out of the nest ... ", "I am a dried houseplant".

7. "Modeling method".

Modeling is based on the principle of replacing real objects with objects, schematic images, signs. The purpose of modeling in environmental education is to ensure the successful assimilation by preschoolers of knowledge about the features of nature objects, their structure and relationships. Preschoolers' cognition of natural phenomena or properties of natural objects can also take place through practical modeling, i.e. experimentation. Using substitute objects, children draw conclusions about why fish have a streamlined shape, why animals have a protective color, why predators need claws.

"Dialogue with nature"

Using the technique of dialogue with nature - aims at the development of the emotional sphere of the child, sensitivity. Dialogues are carried out in various ways - "secret" (children "one on one" communicate with nature) or "open" (oral appeals). "Let's ask the river what kind of fish lives in it", "Ask the butterfly what plants it descended on today"

Another type of modeling is graphical, which helps preschoolers to trace patterns of changes in growth, in the development of living beings, changes in the seasons, and more. For example, the phenological calendars of nature that we keep in the group. It graphically gives a visual representation of the change and signs of the seasons, temperature changes, precipitation at different times of the year, etc. In different age groups, we fill out a calendar of

bird watching, a calendar of onion growth and development, plant seed germination.

Modeling (subject, graphic, practical) forms a deep and meaningful knowledge of natural phenomena, helps to prepare preschoolers for school and maintain continuity in kindergarten and elementary school education.

8. "Mnemonics"

It is better to engage in mnemonics with children 4-5 years old, when they have already accumulated a basic vocabulary, using algorithms for the processes of caring for houseplants, planting seeds, etc. Training is built from simple to complex. We start our work with the simplest mnemonic squares, then move on to mnemonic tracks, and later to mnemonic tables. A mnemotable is a graphic or partially graphic representation of natural phenomena, some actions, fairy tale characters, that is, you can draw what you deem necessary. But to depict so that what is drawn is understandable to children. An example is the mnemonic table: "The journey of a droplet", "Why spring has come", "Who needs water", "Who needs a forest", etc.

9. "Design and research activities"

Design and research activities are also part of the work on environmental education and child rearing. Preschoolers are born researchers. This is the age when a child wants to know everything, he is interested in natural objects, phenomena, relationships in nature. The organization of design and research activities of preschoolers based on environmental material will allow teachers to form key competencies in a child: the ability to see a problem, search and find information, work in a group, talk about results, reflect, compare, answer questions, draw conclusions, establish a causal relationship.

Children are very interested in the project "Adventures of droplets" about the properties of water, during the implementation of which we got acquainted with the properties of water through simple experiments. Implementing the project

"Vegetable garden on the windowsill", in order to bring children to the conclusion about the need for moisture for plant growth, seeds were germinated in two saucers (empty and with wet cotton). To bring children to the conclusion about the need for heat for plant growth, put two identical plants in different conditions: one in a warm place, the other in a cold place and watched their growth. The project activity "Mold is a mushroom" introduced children to a variety of mushrooms. One of the projects successfully implemented in my group is the Forest Kingdom project on familiarization with coniferous plants of the Arkhangelsk region.

10. "Ecological eye - stopper"

An "ecological eye - stopper" eye trap is a bright, extraordinary, eye-catching element or an unusual way of presenting information that attracts attention. Many modern children are distinguished by "clip thinking", brought up by the screen culture of televisions, computers and iPhones. To attract their attention, you need something unusual, bright, eye-catching, that is, a visual stimulus that does not allow you to pass by. We used this feature to create ecological eye-stoppers designed to draw attention, to fix the eye on ecological objects, the interest in which we want to awaken in the child.

Eye -stoppers can be unusual objects, dolls, murals, intriguing inscriptions that children 5-7 years old can already read. The strongest eye-stopper is the color, especially bright, because it is the color of the object that the human eye distinguishes the fastest. A variety of non-standard and funny images of animals, plants, and people are also used. This technique is successfully used in the Centers and corners of independent activity of children to encourage them to independent research activities, as well as on the ecological path (here the eye-stoppers can simultaneously serve as pointers). These can be different types of posters, information leaflets: "Poisonous plants and fungi", "Dangerous insects",

"Take care of your native nature - do not leave garbage behind!", etc.

11. "Ecological storisek"

The ecological storisek "bag of stories" is an interesting modern version of such a traditional form of work with children as "reading aloud". What does a "bag of stories" look like? This is a real canvas bag or backpack, inside of which there is a good illustrated book. The book is complemented by soft toys, props, popular science, encyclopedic literature on the topic, an audio cassette or CD, a didactic or educational game, and much more.

The format of the "ecological storisek" involves choosing a children's ecological fiction book to read aloud and preparing a set of methodological materials for this book, which will undoubtedly help make reading more interesting, and the process of assimilation of environmental knowledge fascinating. We attracted our pupils to read ecological fairy tales - grandmothers. They came in the evening and the children looked forward to meeting them with pleasure. The tasks of storisek are: reading good children's literature of an ecological orientation, expanding the horizons of the child, replenishing the vocabulary, developing skills of meaningful perception of the surrounding world, discussion skills, stimulating interest in nature and environmental activities.

13. "Eco-bag"

As a "bag of stories", an eco-bag sewn with your own hands is well suited. Eco-bag is a bag made of fabric, the simplest design, designed to replace plastic bags. Compared to plastic bags, eco-bags have a lot of advantages: they are reusable, they do not harm the environment and, of course, they look much more beautiful and creative. Having introduced the children to the eco-bag, we talk about how to take another step towards saving nature. We recommended to sew an eco-bag for mothers according to the sketches of children. All wishes were taken into account: material, color, size. Some children applied

a pattern to the eco-bag using special fabric paints and felt-tip pens. In these bags, children brought toys and bird food to kindergarten.

14. "Ecological microphone".

RESULTS

During the conversation, the children, together with the teacher, form a circle and, passing an imitated or toy microphone to each other, express their thoughts on a given environmental topic. All statements of children are accepted, approved, but not discussed. At the end of the game, all statements are summarized. The microphone allows children to freely express their thoughts and feelings. With the help of a microphone, the weakly active children of the group are activated - "The one with the microphone speaks." This form of work helps parents to form a consciously correct attitude to natural phenomena and objects in children, as well as develops critical thinking of preschoolers.

15. "Living Book"

This is a modern version of the traditional form of "meeting evening" with the difference that the "live book" gives you the opportunity to directly communicate with a person (read the "live book") and get an idea of:

- about professions,
- social groups related to ecology;
- about the cleanliness of the environment as an important component of human health and all living things on earth, etc.

"Books" can be ecologists, volunteers, medical workers, local historians, foresters, museum and library workers, writers, poets and other interesting people who have devoted themselves to the problem of environmental protection. Our children really enjoyed meeting with the father of our pupil, who works as a forestry inspector. From his story, the children learned about his profession, about the forest and its protection, were able to ask questions, and together with him planted seeds of coniferous trees of our region. Employees of the district li-

brary have repeatedly visited the children. They carried out work to familiarize children with naturalist writers. During these meetings it was very interesting, because communication with books spiritually enriches a little person, makes him kinder and more beautiful.

16. SORSI

A modern plot-and-display developing sports game that includes a synthesis of various types of activities united by one common plot. The game consists of tests, each test includes two stages: motor and cognitive. The test takes place within 5-7 minutes. Ecological SORSI can be included in the final events in the form of relays: "We will collect edible mushrooms and berries", "We will help to extinguish a fire in the forest", "Clean land, clean river", "Animals of the Red Book" and others".

17. "Information technologies"

When working with preschoolers, you often encounter a lack of information and visual material. In my work with children on ecology, I found a solution - the use of modern information technologies. One of the most accessible means of using computer technology in teaching preschoolers are multimedia presentations, didactic pictures, reproductions of art paintings, photographs, videos, sound recordings (recordings of the voices of birds, mammals, the noise and voices of the forest, surf, rain, wind, etc.). The child, with his visual - imaginative thinking, understands only that it is possible to simultaneously consider, hear, act with the object or evaluate the action of the object. That is why it is so important when teaching preschoolers to turn to the channels of obtaining information available to them, in which children become active, and not passive objects of pedagogical influence.

18. "Creative associations"

In a rapidly changing life, a person is required not only to possess knowledge, but also, first of all, the ability to extract this knowledge himself and operate with it, to think independently and creatively. It is pre-

school children, with their desire to know the world around them, who have great opportunities to develop a moral position in relation to their native land. Therefore, I can consider the creation of a creative association for cognitive research activity "Cognize-ka" innovative in my work, where the child is given complete freedom to manifest cognitive, emotional, social and motor activity in the process of experimentation.

19. "Active forms of work with the family"

The problem of the formation of ecological culture is solved with the help of parents. Parents are invited to classes and celebrations of ecological content, at which they were not just spectators, but also active participants. Such events as: "Let's talk about water", "I planted a tree today - I created the whole world today", "A snail came to visit us", "Ecological microphone" were held. They also gave homework, joint care of animals and plants; collecting collections of natural and other materials; assistance in creating a developing environment; landscaping of plots on the territory of the kindergarten; composing ecological fairy tales and book design; participation in environmental actions (which were described above).

CONCLUSION

During the work, such changes were noticed as: children noticeably expanded their ecological ideas, their ability to establish cause-and-effect relationships; increased interest in objects and phenomena of nature, as well as an emotional reaction to the harmful influence of man on nature, there was a desire to observe norms and rules of behavior in the environment, aimed at preserving the values of nature, there was an interest in the nature of his city, the republic.

Thus, it can be seen that these forms and methods of environmental education of children in preschool and in everyday life are quite effective. Well, the most important thing in environmental education is the personal conviction of the teacher, the ability to interest, awaken in children, edu-

cators and parents the desire to love, protect and protect nature. Thus, it can be concluded that one of the most important conditions for the implementation of the tasks of ecological education of preschoolers is the correct organization and developing subject-spatial environment, which contributes to the cognitive development of the child, ecological and aesthetic development, the formation of environmentally competent behavior of children of their parents in various activities.

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BO'LAJAK PEDAGOG-TARBIYACHILARDA EKOESTETIK MADANIYATNI INNOVATSION EKOLOGIK TA'LIM-TARBIYA ASOSIDA RIVOJLANTIRISH TIZIMINI MODELLASHTIRISH

Annotatsiya. Maqolada bo'lajak o'qituvchilar o'rtasida ekologik-estetik madaniyatning innovatsion ekologik tarbiyasi.

Kalit so'zlar: Shakllantirish, qadriyatlar, shakl, rivojlanish, axloq, shaxsiyat, maktabgacha tarbiyachi, ekoestetika, rivojlanish omillari